

This is a pre-poll and the results will not be saved.

OPERATIONAL RESILIENCE INDEX OF MUSSEL FARMING

Delphi Form 1

The Delphi methodology will allow us to collect and analyse knowledge and opinions from the panel of experts of which we are a part, with more than 20 actors linked to the mussel sector, the academic field, social agents, administration and the environment.

After three rounds of this questionnaire, the aim is to obtain consensus and robust conclusions based on the exchange of ideas for the identification of risk scenarios for the mussel production process in Galicia.

It will only take a few minutes to complete this questionnaire and all your answers will be private and confidential.

The deadline for completing this first round will end on Thursday, July 6, 2023, at 2:00 p.m. If you have any questions or need clarification, you can contact the TransformAr-Galicia team at the email transforma@uvigo.gal or by phone at 986 130 108.

Below is a matrix that contrasts historical data in the rows with future projections of climatic and oceanic-meteorological variables, considered the most relevant by the experts consulted, in relation to their impact on mussel aquaculture. The columns detail the key

phases of the mussel production process, from the collection of the cheek to purification.

*** 1. Using a scale from 0 to 3 , please rate the extent to which the following climatic and oceanic-meteorological elements (and their variation) may negatively affect each of the phases of the mussel production process in the Arousa Estuary. If you wish, you can add additional comments in question 2.**

Where 0 = No negative impact considered; 1 = Low negative impact; 2 = Medium negative impact; 3 = High negative impact.

Please note that some projections are presented with a time horizon that extends up to 2050, while others extend up to the year 2100. This variation in the time horizon is determined by the degree of significance of each projection.

Obtaining cheek from collecting ropes	Obtaining from the rock area	Pre- Stringing	fattening	Unfold	Fattening	Harvest	Washing, sorting and packaging	Registration and transport to the treatment plant	Depuration
---	------------------------------------	-------------------	-----------	--------	-----------	---------	---	--	------------

Air Temperature:

For the period 2011-2020 , the average annual air temperature in Vilanova de Arousa was 15.1°C and there were an average of 40 warm days per year (maximum temperature above 25°C). By 2050 , the average air temperature is expected to be 16.6°C, and we will have an average of approximately 60 warm days per year.

Surface water temperature:

During the period 2011-2020 , there was an average of 49 days/year with a maximum surface water temperature above 20°C in the internal area of the Arousa Estuary and 10 days/year in the external area. By 2050 , an average of 59 days/year with a maximum temperature above 20°C is expected in the

Obtaining cheek from collecting ropes	Obtaining the cheek from the rock area	Pre- Stringing	fattening	Unfold	Fattening	Harvest	Washing, sorting and packaging	Registration and transport to the treatment plant	Depuration
---	---	-------------------	-----------	--------	-----------	---------	---	--	------------

internal area of the estuary and 14 days/year in the external area.

Precipitation:

During the period 2011-2020 , in the Arousa Estuary there were 6.2 days of extreme rainfall per year (over 33.8 litres/m² accumulated daily). For the period 2071-2100 , 8.2 days of extreme rainfall are expected, although the increase will be concentrated in winter and decrease in summer.

Sea level:

During the period 1945-2015 , sea level has risen by 20 cm, with a rate of increase of 2.4 cm/decade. By 2050 , the average sea level will rise by 15-35 cm and by 2100 it will have risen by 0.5-1 m. This represents an average increase of 9.8 cm per decade since 2020.

Note: With every centimetre of sea level rise, 0.5-1 m of sand is lost.

Upwelling :

During the period 2011-2020 , the average volume of water that upwelled in the Ría de Arousa (upwelling index) during April-September (favorable semester for upwelling) was 440 m³ /s/km of coast. By 2050 , an average value of the upwelling index of 480 m³/s/km of coast is expected for the same semester (average increase of 11.25 m³/s/km of coast per decade).

Obtaining cheek from collecting ropes	Obtaining from the rock area	Pre-Stringing	Fattening	Harvest	Washing, sorting and packaging	Registration and transport to the treatment plant	Depuration
---	------------------------------------	---------------	-----------	---------	---	--	------------

Wind:

During the period 2011-2020, there was an average of 35 days/year with wind force 6 or higher (speed greater than 45 km/h) in the outer zone of the estuary and an average of 1 day/year in the inner zone. By 2050, winds of force 6 are expected to be present for 50 days/year in the outer zone. Winds of this intensity are not expected in the inner zone.

Acidification :

During the period 1980-2020, a decrease in pH/decade has been observed in the Arousa Estuary from 8.15 to 8.05 units in the external zone, and from 8.10 to 7.95 units in the internal zone. In 2050, values of 7.95 (exterior) and 7.85 (interior) are expected and by 2100 the pH is expected to fall to 7.8 (exterior) and 7.7 (interior), close to the threshold at which it is corrosive to the shell of mussels and other bivalves (approx. 7.6 units).

Note: A drop in pH of 0.3 units means doubling the acidity of the water.

2. If you wish, you can add any comments or clarifications you consider relevant to the content of the matrix you have covered.

* 3. Informed consent

I agree to the following statements:

- I agree to participate in this study.
- I understand that participation in this study is voluntary.
- I confirm that I have read and understood the background information provided for this study.
- I understand that my data will be used anonymously.

Finish

Powered by [Medallia Agile Research](#)